

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN TRACTOR MANUFACTURING AND AGRICULTURE: CURRENT TRENDS AND PROSPECTS

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Annotation: This study examines the impact of artificial intelligence on the development of agriculture and tractor manufacturing. Modern information and communication technologies are actively being introduced into all spheres of life, including agriculture, where they play a key role in improving production processes and optimizing the operation of agricultural machinery. The use of artificial intelligence makes it possible to develop autonomous tractor control systems, optimize precision farming processes and improve safety in the fields. This overview also covers examples of modern technologies, such as artificial intelligence applications for soil and crop health monitoring, and the use of drones for agricultural land analysis. Understanding these trends is important to improve agricultural efficiency and reduce its negative impact on the environment.

Key words: soil and crops, agricultural production, artificial intelligence, drones;

Аннотация: В данном исследовании рассматривается влияние искусственного интеллекта на развитие сельского хозяйства и тракторостроения. Современные информационно-коммуникационные технологии активно внедряются во все сферы жизни, включая сельское хозяйство, где они играют ключевую роль в улучшении производственных процессов и оптимизации работы сельскохозяйственной техники. Использование искусственного интеллекта позволяет разрабатывать автономные системы управления тракторами, оптимизировать процессы прецизионного земледелия и улучшать безопасность работы на полях. Этот обзор также охватывает примеры современных технологий, таких как приложения на основе искусственного интеллекта для мониторинга состояния почвы и урожая, а также использование дронов для анализа сельскохозяйственных угодий. Понимание этих тенденций имеет важное значение для повышения эффективности сельского хозяйства и снижения его негативного воздействия на окружающую среду.

Ключевые слова: почвы и урожая, сельскохозяйственного производства, искусственный интеллект, дроны;

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot sun'iy intellektning qishloq xo'jaligi va traktor ishlab chiqarish rivojlanishiga ta'sirini o'rganadi. Zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari hayotimizning barcha jabhalariga, jumladan, qishloq xo'jaligiga ham

faol joriy etilmoqda, ular ishlab chiqarish jarayonlarini takomillashtirish va qishloq xo'jaligi texnikalarining ishlashini optimallashtirishda muhim o'rin tutadi. Sun'iy intellektdan foydalanish avtonom traktorlarni boshqarish tizimlarini ishlab chiqish, dehqonchilikning aniq jarayonlarini optimallashtirish va dalalarda xavfsizlikni yaxshilash imkonini beradi. Ushbu sharh shuningdek, tuproq va ekinlarning sog'lig'ini monitoring qilish uchun sun'iy intellekt ilovalari va qishloq xo'jaligi yerlarini tahlil qilish uchun dronlardan foydalanish kabi zamonaviy texnologiyalar misollarini o'z ichiga oladi. Ushbu tendentsiyalarni tushunish qishloq xo'jaligi samaradorligini oshirish va uning atrof-muhitga salbiy ta'sirini kamaytirish uchun muhimdir.

Kalit so'zlar: tuproq va ekinlar, qishloq xo'jaligi ishlab chiqarishi, sun'iy intellekt, dronlar;

The republic is currently taking comprehensive measures to actively develop the digital economy and the widespread introduction of modern information and communication technologies in various industries and areas, including public administration, education, healthcare and agriculture. More than 220 priority projects have already been launched, including improving the e-government system, developing the domestic software and information technology market, as well as the creation of IT parks in all regions of the republic to provide personnel in this area [1].

Today, technologies developed by large companies in the field of agriculture are actively being implemented to create and use equipment for agriculture. Companies such as John Deere, Case, New Holland and others make significant contributions to the development of agricultural machinery.

Soil and crop monitoring systems: Soil quality and nutrition are key to determining the type of crops grown and their quality. Due to increased deforestation, soil quality is deteriorating, making it difficult to assess. German technology startup PEAT has developed an artificial intelligence-based application called Plantix that can detect nutrient deficiencies in soil and identify pests and plant diseases. This app uses image recognition technology to allow farmers to take photos of plants using their smartphones. Similarly, Trace Genomics uses machine learning to help farmers analyze soil health. Such applications allow farmers to monitor the health of soil and plants, increasing productivity levels [2].

Drone-based Crop Health Analysis: SkySquirrel Technologies has introduced Ariel's drone-based visualization solutions for crop health monitoring. Data is collected by a drone and transmitted to a computer for experts to analyze.

Agriculture and livestock farming are among the oldest and most important industries in the world, playing a significant role in the economy. They represent a \$5 trillion turnover and are considered key to the world's population expected to rise to

more than nine billion by 2050. This will require an increase in agricultural production by 70%. Given the limited availability of land, water and other resources, there is a need to be smarter and more efficient in agriculture to ensure food security [2].

The use of artificial intelligence is becoming a key factor in agriculture, including tractor manufacturing. This makes it possible to improve production processes, optimize the operation of agricultural machinery and increase the efficiency of farming.

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